

Uranium (IV) Carboxylates-III. Malate Compounds of Uranium (IV)

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Uranium(IV) dimalate, $U(C_4H_4O_5)_2 \cdot H_2O$ has been prepared by photolytic method. The compound is green crystalline solid, sparingly soluble in water, insoluble in organic solvents but goes into solution when treated with alkali malate solution forming the complex ions, UM_3^{-2} and $U_2M_5^{-2}$. Soluble complex compounds of the types, $R_2[UM_3] \cdot nH_2O$ and $R_2[U_2M_5] \cdot nH_2O$ (where $R = Na^+, K^+$ and NH_4^+ and $M =$ malate ion) are prepared by treating uranium(IV) malate in the aqueous solution of different concentrations of alkali malates. The i.r. spectra of the compounds are recorded and basing on the i.r. data the structures have been suggested.

THE preparation and the characterization of a few uranium(IV) carboxylates have been reported by us in our previous communications^{1,2}. In the present study we report the preparation of uranium(IV) dimalate and a few alkali uranium(IV) malate compounds and their structures have been suggested with the help of i.r. spectral data.

Experimental

(A) Preparation of uranium(IV) dimalate, $U(C_4H_4O_5)_2 \cdot H_2O$:

Uranyl formate (about 2 gms) in aqueous solution was reduced by exposing to sunlight in presence of a few ml. of formic acid and alcohol. The reduced

solution was treated with a solution of malic acid when a precipitate was formed. The resulting solution along with the precipitate formed was further exposed to sunlight for 8-10 hr. The light green compound obtained was filtered, washed with water and finally with ethanol dried in vacuum and analysed. The uranium content of the compound was estimated as U_3O_8 and carboxylate content was estimated by acid alkali titration. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

The compound is green in colour, sparingly soluble in water, insoluble in organic solvents but soluble in aqueous solution of alkali malate forming a green solution. The solubility of the compound increases in solutions containing increasing amount of alkali malate. This may be due to the formation of soluble complex compound containing the ions either UM_3^{-2} or $U_2M_5^{-2}$. Hence attempt was made to prepare

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MOLAR CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF URANIUM(IV) DIMALATE AND THE COMPLEX SALTS

Name and formula of the compounds	Uranium%		Carboxylate%		Nitrogen%		molar conductivity mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻² ohm ⁻¹
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
1. Uranium(IV)dimalate, $UM_2 \cdot H_2O$	45.38	45.77	50.46	50.77	—	—	—
2. Sodium tris(malato)uranate(IV) $Na_2[UM_3] \cdot H_2O$	34.02	34.10	37.49	37.82	—	—	240
3. Potassium tris(malato)uranate(IV), $K_2[UM_3] \cdot H_2O$	33.04	33.60	35.65	36.16	—	—	293
4. Ammonium tris(malato)uranate(IV), $(NH_4)_2[UM_3] \cdot 3H_2O$	32.78	32.88	36.42	36.47	4.03	4.97	291
5. Sodium penta(malato)diuranate(IV), $Na_2[U_2M_5] \cdot H_2O$	37.76	37.42	41.28	41.51	—	—	232
6. Potassium penta(malato)diuranate(IV), $K_2[U_2M_5] \cdot 5H_2O$	37.18	36.51	40.77	40.50	—	—	290
7. Ammonium penta(malato)diuranate(IV), $(NH_4)_2[U_2M_5] \cdot 2H_2O$	40.87	39.41	43.44	43.71	2.75	2.98	253

M = Malate ion.

the salts of uranium(IV) containing the complex ions, UM_3^{-2} and $U_2M_5^{-2}$ in solid state.

(B) Preparation of complex salts of the types, $R_2[UM_3]$, nH_2O and $R_2[U_2M_5]nH_2O$ (where $R = Na^+$, K^+ and NH_4^+):

Uranium(IV) dimalate, was added to the aqueous solution of alkali malate in the molar ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2. At room temperature it was less soluble but went into solution on heating forming a deep green solution. Then it was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated at low temperature. A dirty green mass was obtained. It was washed with alcohol 2-3 times and dried in vacuum and analysed. The uranium and the malate content of the complexes were determined as described earlier. The analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Conductivity measurements were made with a Philip's conductivity bridge and a dipped type cell (Cell constant 1.2). The molar conductance values of the complexes were recorded in Table 1 along with the analytical data. The i.r. spectra of the complexes have been recorded in potassium bromide phase.

Uranium(IV) dimalate is very slightly soluble in water. The solubility in water at 26° was found to be 3.97×10^{-3} gm.mole per litre and the pH of the saturated solution was 2.9. The low pH indicates the liberation of acid due to dissociation of the compound in water. The acid properties of uranium(IV) dimalate shown by low pH of its aqueous solutions

can be explained by the fact that some of the water molecules are directly bound to uranium and undergo protonic dissociation. The probable reaction being:

The equilibrium constant (K) of the reaction (2) is found to be 3.48×10^{-6} .

Uranium(IV) dimalate goes into solution forming a green solution when it is added to the aqueous solution of alkali malate. This property of the dimalate was utilised to prepare the complex salts of the ions, UM_3^{-2} and $U_2M_5^{-2}$. The formation of the complex ions in solution may be due to the reaction of more malate ion with uranium(IV) ion. The solubility of uranium(IV) dimalate in different concentrations of sodium malate solution was determined at room temperature and the equilibrium constant (K) was calculated. The average K value is 4.735×10^3 at temperature 26°.

Discussion

The complex compound of the type, $R_2[UM_3]$, nH_2O and $R_2[U_2M_5]$, nH_2O (where $R = Na^+$, K^+ and NH_4^+ and $M =$ malate ion) prepared in the present study are all salt like formed by the ions R^+ and either UM_3^{-2} or $U_2M_5^{-2}$. The dissociation of the complexes in aqueous solution can be represented by the following equations:

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL I.R. BANDS OF URANIUM(IV) DIMALATE AND THE COMPLEX MALATE SALTS

UM_2, H_2O	$Na_2[UM_3], H_2O$	$Na_2[U_2M_5], 5H_2O$	$K_2[UM_3], H_2O$	$K_2[U_2M_5], 5H_2O$	$(NH_4)_2[U_2M_5], 2H_2O$	Malic acid
3300 s	3500 s(bd)	3600 s(bd)	3600 s(bd)	3600 s(bd)	3500 s(bd) 3400 s	
1560 vs	1655 s(s) 1600 s 1545 sh 1535 sh	1670 sh(s) 1640 sh 1600 s 1560 sh 1540 sh 1520 sh 1510 w	1665 sh 1600 s 1555 sh 1540 sh	1665 sh(s) 1626 sh 1600 s 1560 sh(s) 1540 sh 1520 sh 1510 w	1660 sh(s) 1630 sh(s) 1600 s 1660 sh 1540 sh 1520 w	1750 (s)
1406 w(sh)	1445 s 1410 sh	1460 s 1420 sh	1460 s 1410 sh	1460 s 1420 sh	1460 s 1415 sh	
1316 sh	1330 sh	1340 sh	1330 sh	1360 sh 1340 sh	1340 sh	1320 (m)
1250 w(s) 1190 w	1250 w(sh) 1190 w	1260 sh 1200 w	1190 w	1190 w	1190 w	1218 (w) 1180 (m) 1100 m
1085 s 1034 w 975 w(sh) 930 s 803 w	1080 s 1034 m 969 m 930 w 890 s 840 w 800 s 700 w	1085 s 1040 m 970 m 935 m 895 s 842 w 805 w 710 w	1080 s 1038 m 968 m 930 w 890 s 840 w 800 w 700 w	1080 s 1040 m 970 m 930 w 890 s 840 w 800 w 700 m	1080 s 1037 m 970 m 930 w 890 s 840 w 800 w 700 m	965 (m) 885 (m)
715 w(sh)	700 w	710 w	700 w	700 m	700 m	

But in certain cases the values are higher which can be explained that the complexes undergo hydrolysis in aqueous solution which is known from the pH drop of the aqueous solutions of the complexes with time. The pH change can be explained first of all by the displacement of the malate group by the water molecules and secondly by the fact that intrasphere water in the uranium(IV) region undergoes protonic dissociation.

So with time the number of ions in the aqueous solution of the complex increases, hence the molar conductivity data increases with time.

The vibrational bands of malic acid and uranium (IV) dimalate and the complex salts are recorded in Table 2. All of these complexes show a strong and broad band in the region 3300–3600 cm^{-1} , which may be attributed to O–H stretching vibration of associated water molecules or the OH vibrations of secondary alcoholic group of malic acid. The broadness of the band further manifest either intra or intramolecular hydrogen bonding in these complexes.

The next important vibrational band is found in the region 1560–1690 cm^{-1} in all the complexes and arises due to antisymmetric (O–C–O) stretching vibrations. In the free acid this band appears at 1705 cm^{-1} . Shifting of the band to lower frequency

region in the metal complexes and their sharpness clearly imply that both the carboxylate groups of malic acid are coordinated to uranium(IV) ion. The bands in the 1550–1600 cm^{-1} are attributed to (OH) deformation vibrations in these complexes and the bands in the region 1450 cm^{-1} arises due to symmetric stretching vibrations of the (O–C–O) groups. The next two bands of malic acid sensitive to coordination are found at 1180 and 1100 cm^{-1} respectively and are of medium intensity. It is believed that the former arises due to OH deformation and the latter due to (C–O) stretching vibration of the secondary alcoholic groups. In the complexes while the former shifts to higher frequency region, the latter is found to move towards lower frequency region. Such features are reminiscent of coordination of the secondary alcoholic group with the uranium(IV) ion in these complexes.

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